

BIOFIN-EU-project.eu

PROTECTING AND RESTORING BIODIVERSITY USING MAINSTREAM FINANCE

D4.4 NbS Decision Support Tool (NbS Dashboard)

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Executive Summary

This document introduces the initial version of the NbS Decision Support Tool, referred to in the project proposal as the NbS Dashboard. The NbS Dashboard is a digital platform designed to support biodiversity-informed financial decision-making.

The primary purpose of this document is to provide access to a prototype version of the dashboard (commonly referred to as the BIOFIN-EU MVP), source code repositories, and supporting documentation such as infrastructure diagrams and requirements specifications. These materials reflect work carried out by Work Package 4 (WP4) and the wider BIOFIN-EU consortium during the first 18 months of the project.

The development of the prototype has been guided by extensive collaboration among project partners, early research across learning sites, and engagement with potential end-users. This version is intended to test core concepts, validate design assumptions, and define functional and non-functional requirements in preparation for a future production release.

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
ES	Ecosystem Services
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
NbS	Nature Based Solution(s)
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
DoA	Description of Action
ML	Machine Learning

CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
TNFD	Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures
TCFD	Taskforce on Climate-related Financial Disclosures
ESG	Environment Social Governance

1. Introduction

BIOFIN-EU aims to unlock conventional financial flows with the objective of reversing biodiversity loss, in alignment with the European Green Deal priorities and in particular the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and the 2030 Climate Target Plan. The project will enhance the implementation of the sustainable finance taxonomy, thereby mainstreaming biodiversity and ecosystem services into society and the economy. The project will develop financial solutions to address societal challenges, including through innovative funding approaches for Nature-based Solutions (NbS).

At the core of the key objectives is the development of the BIOFIN-EU Dashboard, a digital software tool designed to help actors (including investors and NbS providers, financial and accounting experts, private and public beneficiaries, ecologists and data scientists) navigate large-scale financing challenges and to develop, replicate, scale out and strengthen NbS investment, creating a more sustainable, vibrant, resilient and healthy planet and supporting the EU's biodiversity restoration ambitions.

The dashboard will enable an NbS provider seeking full or partial financing for biodiversity initiatives (i.e. a specific NbS) to develop a business case using associated information and data with the explicit goal of attracting and connecting with potential funders (e.g. a bank or hedge fund manager). The dashboard will provide the funder with data, decision workflow tools, and analytics while enabling risk calculation and scenario analysis across one or more NbS.

1.1. Scope

As outlined in the Executive Summary, this deliverable provides access to a prototype version of the BIOFIN-EU dashboard, along with key technical resources such as infrastructure diagrams. For each resource, supporting information is provided, including a high-level overview, defined objectives, and, where applicable, key functional highlights.

Please note that the resources provided via this deliverable are under continuous review and development. Source code, interfaces, and documentation are therefore subject to change; however, all resources are version-controlled to ensure that previous iterations can be accessed and reverted to where necessary.

1.2. Deliverable versions

This document is the first version of the "NbS Decision Support Tool (NbS Dashboard)" deliverable, submitted in June 2025 (Month 18). The Description of Action (DoA) includes a

second version of this deliverable to be completed by Month 36. Details of specific amendments and additions will be included in a new section of the updated version.

2. Overview of Technical Resources

Table 1.0 provides a high-level overview of the technical resources referenced in this document.

Each resource is then described in a dedicated section to offer key contextual information. It is recommended that readers review this information before accessing the corresponding resource.

Resource	Resource URL	Resource Type	Access
BIOFIN-EU Documentation Wiki	https://github.com/BIOFIN-EU/documentation/wiki/Home-Page	GitHub Wiki	Open
BIOFIN-EU MVP Dashboard	https://biofin.mvp.137.120.31.148.nip.io/home/	Website	Open
BIOFIN-EU MVP Source Code Repository	https://github.com/BIOFIN-EU/MVP	GitHub Repository	Open
BIOFIN-EU MVP Reusable Docker Images	https://github.com/orgs/BIOFIN-EU/packages/container/package/biofin-mvp	Docker Images Repository	Open
<p>Table 1.0 provides a high-level overview of the technical resources referenced in this document.</p>			

3. BIOFIN-EU Documentation Wiki

3.1. Overview

The BIOFIN-EU Documentation Wiki is the central knowledge base to store documentation related to the BIOFIN-EU platform, its Minimum Viable Product (MVP) and future developments on the production version of the BIOFIN-EU Dashboard.

Based in GitHub, it provides structured and version-controlled access to technical, functional, and operational documentation, supporting both development and stakeholder engagement. The wiki is designed to ensure clarity, consistency, and traceability throughout the development lifecycle of the BIOFIN-EU Dashboard.

For the avoidance of doubt, technical documentation of source code repositories is not included in the BIOFIN-EU Documentation Wiki. Such documentation will reside in the code base itself, for example in the readme.md file of the “BIOFIN-EU MVP Source Code Repository” introduced in section 5.

3.2. Objectives

- Serve as the single source of truth for BIOFIN-EU technical and functional documentation.
- Support onboarding of new developers, contributors, and partners with clearly organised resources.
- Document processes, infrastructure setup, requirements, and decisions to support continuity and transparency.
- Provide reusable templates for requirements gathering and feature definition.

3.3. Access Information

- URL: <https://github.com/BIOFIN-EU/documentation/wiki/Home-Page>

3.4. Key resources

- High level designs for software infrastructure, using the C4 Model (www.C4model.com) approach.

- Links to requirements documents, namely the BIOFIN-EU MVP Use Case
- Information regarding key terminology including definition of the user groups and personas who will interact with the BIOFIN-EU dashboard.
- Information regarding the technical stack and approach to dashboard deployments
- Templates for requirements and feature definition, to be referenced during the development of the production version of the platform.

4. BIOFIN-EU MVP

4.1. Overview

The BIOFIN-EU Dashboard MVP serves as a functional prototype of the digital platform envisioned within the BIOFIN-EU project. It provides a minimal yet operational interface that demonstrates core concepts, supports initial stakeholder engagement, and validates design decisions in collaboration with project partners. The MVP has been developed to test user interactions, technical feasibility, and integration capabilities with relevant EU datasets and taxonomies, laying the groundwork for more advanced features in future iterations.

4.2. Objectives

- Establish a working backend to support future data layers and interactions
- Create a minimal web interface to validate early design assumptions
- Build and test defined use cases created in collaboration with WP2 and WP5.
- Collect initial user impressions from consortium partners and potential users

4.3. Access Information

- URL: <https://biofin.mvp.137.120.31.148.nip.io/home/>
- Hosted by: University of Maastricht

4.4. Functional Highlights

- A basic **frontend dashboard** allowing users to create and maintain accounts.
- The ability for an NbS Provider (i.e. a Borrower) to create a profile for their NbS site and provide key information.
- Mock-ups for a use case of two example Banks (ABN Amro and RaboBank) integrating the BIOFIN dashboard into their own websites, redirecting customers to undergo a “Green Loan Checker”. Users can access this use case via the “Use Case 1 (Third Iteration)” option on the left-hand menu of the dashboard, via the URL above.

- Integration with the EU Taxonomy Compass API, ensuring that the dashboard reflects the most up-to-date definitions and criteria for sustainable economic activities under the EU Taxonomy.
- Integration with the EARLC14 statistical dataset (Ecological status of monitored river water bodies at Catchment Level), enabling users to select specific geographic regions on the map and retrieve the latest water quality information relevant to those areas.
- Under development, a RESTful API to facilitate the integration with external services, allowing access and management of the NbS products (<https://biofin.mvp.137.120.31.148.nip.io/api/v1/>). For the avoidance of doubt, this API is purely for prototype and testing purposes. A production version will be developed and implemented in the production version of the dashboard.
- Interactions between NbS Providers (Borrowers) and NbS Funders (Lenders)

5. BIOFIN-EU MVP Source Code Repository

5.1. Overview

The BIOFIN-EU MVP dashboard is a web-based application designed to support the exploration and evaluation of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) within the project's scope. The source code has been developed with a strong emphasis on robustness, modularity, and maintainability, leveraging industry-standard frameworks and tools to ensure long-term sustainability and ease of collaboration across the consortium.

The architecture adheres to best practices inspired by the Twelve-Factor App methodology (<https://12factor.net/>), promoting portability, scalability, and deployment consistency across various environments.

5.2. Objectives

The primary objective of the MVP source code is to provide a solid technical foundation for the BIOFIN-EU dashboard that:

- Ensures reliable and consistent deployment across different environments.
- Facilitates rapid iteration and testing through mock data and preconfigured setups.
- Supports modularity and future extensibility of both front-end and back-end components.
- Facilitates future collaboration through planned open-source licensing, with the code base set to be released under the Apache 2.0 license once it reaches a stable version.
- Enables integration with spatial analysis tools to support geolocation-based decision-making and facilitate connectivity with existing open EU databases, such as those providing water quality statistics and ecosystem pressure data, through standardised geospatial referencing.

5.3. Access Information

The BIOFIN-EU code base is hosted on a private GitHub repository, with plans to release it under the Apache 2.0 open-source license upon reaching a stable release milestone. The repository includes:

- Link to the code base in GitHub: <https://github.com/BIOFIN-EU/MVP>
- Link to docker container images in GitHub: <https://github.com/orgs/BIOFIN-EU/packages/container/package/biofin-mvp>

5.4. Functional Highlights

While the main user-facing functionalities of the dashboard are described in section 3, the MVP source code offers a number of technical features and capabilities:

- A readme.md page explaining how to deploy a local version of the software (<https://github.com/BIOFIN-EU/MVP/blob/main/README.md>)
- Built using the Django web framework, recognised for its reliability and scalability in enterprise-grade applications.
- Exposes a RESTful API via the Django REST Framework, enabling external integrations and programmatic access to data.
- Utilises Bootstrap 5 to ensure responsive design and an accessible user experience across a range of devices and screen sizes.
- Integrates geospatial libraries including Shapely, GeoJSON, and PyProj to handle geolocation data and spatial projections.
- Employs PostgreSQL 16.3 as the primary database engine, ensuring robust and secure data storage.
- The use of environment variables and .env files aligns with modern development practices for configuration management.
- Fully containerised using Docker and orchestrated with Docker Compose, enabling reproducible development and deployment across platforms.